

Cornel West's Views on the Philosophical Value of Democratic Rights

Dr. P. Shobha

Assistant Professor (C)
Dept of English
Telangana Mahila Viswavidyalayam

Abstract:

*Cornel West is an American philosopher, political activist, social critic, author, and public intellectual who has focused on the role of race, gender, and class in American society and the means by which people act and react to their fundamental conditions. His most influential books are *Race Matters* (1994) and *Democracy Matters* (2004) these books are much about the crisis of black people's leadership and winning the fight against imperialism. West is an outspoken voice in American leftist politics he always called the U.S. a racist patriarchal nation where still we can find white supremacy which continues to define everyday life. The blacks are made weak-willed which ensures their racial justice to White American who has resisted fully accepting the humanity of blacks.*

West has also given his view about the September 11 attacks which made the blacks feel unsafe and unprotected among the white Americans it was an ugly terrorist attack on innocent civilians on 9/11, which made the whole country sink into the thought of blues. West being a member of the Campaign for Peace and Democracy, deals with the issues of modernized slavery and human trafficking. He wanted to gain freedom for everyday and all colour people so that they can see and understand their rights through a different lens and understand what is happening around their surroundings.

Key Words: Democracy, race, identity, and civil rights

Cornel Ronald West (born June 2, 1953) is an American philosopher, political activist, social critic, author, and public intellectual. West focuses on the role of race, gender, and class in American society and the means by which people act and react to their radical condition. Among his most influential books are *Race Matters* (1994) and *Democracy Matters* (2004). Cornel West is a prominent and provocative democratic intellectual. He is a Professor of the Practice of Public Philosophy at Harvard University and holds the title of

Professor Emeritus at Princeton University. Cornel West graduated Magna Cum Laude from Harvard in three years and obtained his M.A. and Ph.D. in Philosophy at Princeton.

West is an outspoken voice in American leftist politics, and as such has been critical of members of the Democratic Party, including former President Barack Obama and Hillary Clinton.

West has called the U.S. a "racist patriarchal" nation where white supremacy continues to define everyday life. "White America," he writes, "has been historically weak-willed in ensuring racial justice and has continued to resist fully accepting the humanity of blacks." This has resulted, he says, in the creation of many "degraded and oppressed people hungry for identity, meaning, and self-worth." West attributes most of the black community's problems to "existential angst derive[d] from the lived experience of ontological wounds and emotional scars inflicted by white supremacist beliefs and images permeating U.S. society and culture.

In West's view, the September 11 attacks gave white Americans a glimpse of what it means to be a black person in the United States—feeling "unsafe, unprotected, subject to random violence, and hatred" for who they are. "The ugly terrorist attacks on innocent civilians on 9/11," he said, "plunged the whole country into the blues. West was arrested on October 13, 2014, while protesting against the shooting of Michael Brown and participating in Ferguson October, and again on August 10, 2015, while demonstrating outside a courthouse in St. Louis on the one-year anniversary of Brown's death. Cornel West publicly supported the 2008 Democratic presidential candidate, Senator Barack Obama.

West, however, criticized President Obama when Obama won the Nobel Peace Prize in 2009, saying that it would be difficult for Obama to be "a war president with a peace prize". West further retracted his support for Obama in an April 2011 interview, stating that Obama is "a black mascot of Wall Street oligarchs and a black muppet of corporate plutocrats. And now he has become head of the American killing machine and is proud of it in blackface."

Cornel West believes that philosophy should engage existential issues about the meaning of life as well as ethical (fair) issues about power, freedom, democracy and equality in society. In other words, he believes that philosophy should make us examine ourselves as well as the world we live in.

In his book, Cornel West addresses many issues in today's society regarding African Americans. West states that one of the major issues is "Nihilism in Black America", where many African Americans have a sense of worthlessness. Instead of blaming a certain group,

West calls on African Americans, Whites, Liberals, Conservatives, and more to take an action against the epidemic that is racism. Throughout the book, West constantly refers to the essential aspects needed for African Americans to win the battle against racism in different forms, which are: Pride, Unity, and Love. Major ideas conveyed in the book include: the quality of Black Leadership, too little self-love, uniting for a bigger cause rather than fighting with each other, stopping seeing themselves through "white lenses", and overall, acknowledging the existence of racism, in order to deal with it

"Without hope, there can be no failure, that without meaning there can be no struggle"

Cornel West in *Race Matters* has pointed out:

"Race is the most explosive issue in American life precisely because it forces us to confront the tragic facts of poverty and paranoia, despair, and distrust." (8)

Race Matters by Cornel West is a seminal work that critically examines the issues of race and racial inequality in the United States. Published in 1993, the book addresses systemic racism, social injustice, and the challenges faced by African Americans in contemporary society. West explores various aspects of racial dynamics, including the impact of institutional structures, economic disparities, and cultural factors. Through a combination of insightful analysis and personal reflections, West encourages readers to confront the realities of racism and engage in meaningful dialogue about social change.

On the other hand, *Democracy Matters* by Cornel West takes a broader perspective, shifting its focus to the overarching theme of democracy. Published later in 2004, this book explores the state of democracy in the modern world, particularly in the context of the United States. West argues that democracy is under threat, identifying what he calls "three dominating antidemocratic dogmas." These include free-market fundamentalism, which he critiques by drawing parallels with extreme right-wing religious fundamentalism. West contends that these ideologies pose significant challenges to the principles of democracy, emphasizing the need for a critical examination of these forces.

While *Race Matters* specifically zooms in on racial issues and their implications, "Democracy Matters" expands its scope to encompass broader concerns about the health and sustainability of democracy itself. In this later work, West extends his critique to address political, economic, and cultural factors that impact the democratic ideals he believes are crucial for a just and equitable society. The two books collectively offer readers a

comprehensive exploration of societal challenges, encouraging critical reflection and dialogue on issues related to race, democracy, and social justice.

The continuing experience of discrimination, the unfulfilled dreams of integration, and internalized self-hatred create a feeling of rejection that pervades the African American world. An interesting point that Cornel West makes is that if you are a woman and your skin is dark, you are very likely going to find yourself at the lower end of the socioeconomic ladder in this country. The concept of race in the connections between race, class, and gender in *Race Matters* is very apparent in the reports that fill our daily newspapers. West asserts that "Without the presence of black people in America, European-Americans would not be "white" - they would be only Irish, Italians, Poles, Welsh, and others engaged in class, ethnic, and gender struggles."

Cornel West sees this devaluing of existence, of one's own and of the other's, black and white, as one of the most pressing problems facing our country. When a segment of the population no longer believes in the foundations of society, they will become a force to subvert it. This is not exclusively a black problem. The riots in L.A. after the Rodney King verdict may be a chilling sign of things to come. The drug war, in large measure, is a covert race war being fought in our city streets. In Dr. West's words, "The self-fulfilling prophecy of the nihilistic threat is that without hope, there can be no future, that without meaning there can be no struggle."

Rejection is not new to African American culture. The soul-quenching ordeal of slavery provided little personal meaning or value. The assertion that rejection is not new to African American culture reflects a historical and cultural context shaped by the deeply traumatic experience of slavery. The reference to the "soul-quenching ordeal of slavery" alludes to the institution that marked a significant part of African American history, particularly in the United States. Slavery, which persisted for centuries, was a dehumanizing system that subjected African Americans to extreme forms of exploitation, brutality, and devaluation. The institution was built on the rejection of their basic human rights, individuality, and dignity. Enslaved individuals were considered property rather than people, devoid of personal agency, and subjected to systematic degradation. These aspects highlight the profound impact of slavery on the psychological and cultural aspects of African American identity. Slavery, as an institution, not only rejected the humanity of African Americans but also denied them the ability to find personal significance and value in their experiences. It stripped away their autonomy, cultural

heritage, and familial connections, leaving a void in the construction of personal meaning. The aftermath of slavery continued to present challenges as African Americans faced systemic racism, discrimination, and social inequality. The rejection ingrained in the institution of slavery permeated through subsequent generations, contributing to enduring struggles for recognition, justice, and equal rights.

In a broader sense, this statement underscores the resilience of African American culture in the face of historical trauma. Despite the profound rejection embedded in the legacy of slavery, African American communities have forged resilient identities, celebrated cultural heritage, and contributed significantly to the cultural tapestry of the United States. Understanding the historical context allows for a deeper appreciation of the strength and endurance demonstrated by African Americans in the ongoing quest for justice, equality, and cultural affirmation. Again, Dr. West's words:

"The genius of our black foremothers and forefathers was to create powerful buffers to ward off the nihilistic threat, to equip black folk with cultural Armor to beat back the demons of hopelessness, meaninglessness and lovelessness. These buffers consisted of cultural structures of meaning and feeling that created sustained communities; this Armor constituted ways of life and struggle that embodied values of service and sacrifice, love and care, discipline and excellence". (23)

Traditionally, the black religious and civic institutions have been that anchor and source of sanity.

The seventies marked the beginning of the decline of these institutions, which he attributes to what he calls "a saturation of the market forces and market moralities in black life and the present crisis in black leadership". The "saturation of market forces" implies a pervasive influence of economic dynamics, shaping various facets of African American life. This influence might have manifested in shifts towards a more market-driven approach in matters such as employment, education, and community development. The increased emphasis on market forces could have resulted in a commodification of elements within black culture, potentially altering or diminishing traditional values and communal practices. Economic considerations and individual pursuits may have taken precedence over collective well-being, contributing to a transformative period.

Simultaneously, the infiltration of "market moralities" into black life signifies the adoption of values associated with a market-oriented mindset. This shift may have led to an

increased focus on competition, individual success, and profit-driven motives within the community. The influence of market-driven values could have impacted social dynamics and interpersonal relationships, potentially altering the cohesive fabric of African American communities.

The consequence of these intertwined factors was a crisis in black leadership, marking a turning point for institutions that had played crucial roles in the community's development. The decline observed during the seventies reflected not only economic shifts but also a reorientation of values, posing challenges to the traditional foundations of African American institutions and their broader societal roles. The same forces at work throughout America - distrust of leaders and politicians, self-interested pursuit of the bluebird of happiness, and retreat from the public sphere of concern - take an even heavier toll on black institutions. As individuals retreat from advocating for their collective concerns, their leaders lose power to influence social policy. The Reginald Denny beating revealed the intensity of these feelings waiting for some event to cause the pot to boil over. Today we see a resurgence of Black Nationalism and a trend toward segregation as a form of self-protection. Louis Farrakhan's leadership is an example of what Dr. West calls "racial reasoning".

Democracy Matters: Winning the Fight Against Imperialism constitutes seven interrelated chapters that target the liberal/progressive wing of the Democratic Party. In "Democracy Matters," Cornel West diverges from his earlier work, "Race Matters," by shifting the focus from race to a broader examination of democracy in the United States and the global context. The narrative takes a personal turn when West recounts his own experiences, notably the challenges faced at Harvard University, leading to his return to Princeton. However, the central theme revolves around democracy, with West delving into its complexities and the broader implications for the nation and the world. The absence of an extensive discussion on race, a departure from West's previous work, is conspicuous. Instead, he underscores the significance of democracy and its critical role in shaping the trajectory of societies. Nevertheless, the subtext introduces a complicating factor—the fight against imperialism. This layer adds nuance to the overarching message of democracy, reflecting the intertwined nature of political struggles and the broader context in which democratic ideals are pursued.

The narrative becomes further entangled as West addresses a myriad of issues, including the senseless Iraqi War, the continuation of Nixonian Republican tactics through

the Committee to Re-Elect the President (CREEP), and the United States' slide into bankruptcy. The quick concession of Kerry, aligning with his perceived waffler typecast, and the simultaneous decline of poverty-alleviation programs contribute to the complexity of West's defense of American democracy, especially in the aftermath of the 2004 election.

Despite his earnest effort to advocate for democracy, the accumulating challenges and adversities paint a somewhat comical picture of the state of American affairs. The confluence of these disparate elements creates a narrative where the defense of democracy is not a straightforward task, but rather a nuanced and multifaceted endeavor. West's exploration extends beyond the personal, delving into the intricate web of political, economic, and social forces that shape the democratic landscape, making "Democracy Matters" a compelling and intricate commentary on the complexities of contemporary American society.

Democracy Matters is published by the ubiquitous, worldwide Penguin Press, unlike the much smaller Beacon Press of Boston, the publisher of *Race Matters*. Not long by any standard, be it pica or page, *Democracy Matters* comes in at just over 200 pages. *Race Matters*, at just over 100 pages of smaller type, was comprised of pieces previously published in periodicals and anthologies. As indicated by the absence of any credits, the seven titled chapters of *Democracy Matters* are all new to this volume. The reviewer suspects that at least a few of these chapters may have been preceded by talks, speeches, or perhaps media commentary in the more than ten-year span between books.

Without an introduction or a preface, *Democracy Matters* starts off with "Democracy Matters are Frightening in Our Time," with a brief quote from Walt Whitman saying something to the effect that the word *democracy* was yet to be defined, in his day, of course. The word and concept go back to ancient Greece, but at that time democracy was dependent on an elite that has never subsided, even in the face of the literary promise of a new democracy in the original colonies of the United States. West feels that democracy, nowadays, is endangered, and he sees at play "three dominating antidemocratic dogmas." The first, "free-market fundamentalism," cleverly compares the capitalism of corporations, e.g., Enron, with extreme right-wing religious fundamentalism.

Democracy Matters by Cornel West stands as a notable departure from his previous work, *Race Matters*, not only in its thematic focus but also in its publisher and length. The shift to a larger platform with Penguin Press signifies the broader reach and impact West

aims to achieve with his exploration of democracy. While *Race Matters* comprised shorter pieces previously published elsewhere, the chapters in *Democracy Matters* are entirely new to this volume, suggesting a fresh and consolidated perspective on the subject. The absence of an introduction or preface leaves readers to delve directly into the heart of West's concerns about democracy in our time. Opening with a quote from Walt Whitman, the author underscores the ongoing struggle to define democracy. West contends that democracy faces threats, particularly from what he terms as "three dominating antidemocratic dogmas." He skillfully draws parallels between free-market fundamentalism and right-wing religious fundamentalism, highlighting the entwined challenges posed by capitalism and extreme religious ideologies.

Democracy Matters serves as a timely critique of the contemporary threats to democratic ideals, offering insights into the dangers posed by influential forces. The brevity of the book, just over 200 pages, belies the depth of West's analysis and his attempt to navigate the intricate landscape of modern democracy. The suspicion that some chapters may have evolved from talks or media commentary over the preceding decade adds a layer of dynamism to the collection. In this succinct and thought-provoking exploration, West engages readers with his perspective on the evolving nature of democracy, urging them to consider the pressing challenges and ideologies that shape the democratic landscape. The absence of repetition and the concise summarization of the key points reinforce the urgency and relevance of *Democracy Matters* as a critical examination of the contemporary threats to democratic principles.

References:

- West, Cornel. *Race Matters*. Pub: Penguin Books. 2001
- *Democracy Matters*. Pub: Penguin Books 2004.